

Table 2. Effect of N level on LAI, unfilled grain percentage, and grain yield. IARI, 1988 kharif.

N level (kg/ha)	LAI	Unfilled spikelets (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	3.06	11.92	4.64
50	3.80	13.75	5.20
100	4.10	16.60	5.87
LSD (0.05)	0.67	2.08	0.39

LAI (source) due to applied N, however, led to a larger gap between grain number/m² and spikelet number/m². This resulted in a higher sterility percentage (Table 2). □

Rice varieties direct-seeded in puddled soil during boro season in West Bengal

A. K. Mitra, A. Roy, and S. K. B. Roy, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

Boro season rice in West Bengal grows with supplemental irrigation during Nov-May after the wet season rice harvest in lowland and deepwater ecosystems. The area under boro rice has increased from 0.3 million ha in 1980 to 0.7 million ha in 1990. Average grain yield is 4.5 t/ha.

We direct-seeded 11 modern semidwarf rices in puddled soil at Chinsurah to decrease irrigation costs during boro 1985–86. Three methods were used: direct seeding of nonsprouted seed (NSD), direct seeding of sprouted seed (SD), and seedbed with sprouted seed and subsequent transplanting (SST). We sowed the nonsprouted seed 4 d before the sprouted seed.

Crop duration was slightly less under NSD (142 d) than under SD (146 d); plants in SST matured at 158 d (see table). Growth duration for HPU741, IR36, and IR60 differed more (26–27 d) than that for IET4786, IR56, and CR126-42-1 (12–14 d). Grain yield was approximately the same, but some varieties—IR36, IR50, CR126-42-1, and IET5851—yielded higher (5.2–5.6 t/ha) under NSD. IR56, IR60, and IET1444 yielded higher under SD, while IET4094 and IET4786 yielded higher under SST.

Results indicate that early harvest of direct seeded rice is possible without

Yield and growth duration of some rice varieties under 3 systems of crop establishment. Chinsurah, India, 1985–86 boro.

Variety	Duration ^a (d)				Grain yield (t/ha)			
	NSD	SD	SST	(NSD-SST)	NSD	SD	SST	Mean
Dular	120	123	132	12	2.0	2.2	2.9	2.4
CR126-42-1	144	144	158	14	5.2	4.3	4.3	4.6
IET1444	144	150	158	14	4.3	5.6	4.3	4.7
IET5851	142	144	158	16	5.2	4.5	4.6	4.7
HPU741	136	140	162	26	4.8	4.0	4.0	4.3
IR36	136	155	163	27	5.3	5.2	4.7	5.0
IR50	150	151	162	12	5.6	5.3	4.9	5.2
IR56	150	151	162	12	5.3	5.7	4.5	5.2
IR60	136	140	163	27	4.8	5.6	4.7	5.0
IET4786	151	156	163	12	4.7	5.4	5.6	5.2
IET4094	156	157	162	6	4.3	5.5	6.1	5.3
Mean	142	146	158	16	4.7	4.8	4.6	5.3

^aSeeding dates were 9 Dec, 13 Dec, and 13 Dec; transplanting date was 13 Jan.

sacrificing grain yield. Compared with transplanting, direct seeding shortens the growth duration an average of 16 d, and

saves four to five irrigations during the reproductive phase. □

Variation in rice husk-kernel ratio (HKR)

R. K. Das and N. M. Miah, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

Increasing the ratio of grain to biomass (harvest index [HI]) is a way to improve rice yields in the tropics. Reduced partitioning of dry weight to the husk could improve HI.

We examined seasonal variations in HKR in modern rice varieties BR1, BR3,

BR9, BR12, and BR16 grown at the BRRI farm during the 1985–86 transplanted aus, transplanted aman, and boro seasons. Plots had four 5.4-m rows each with 25- × 20-cm spacing and were laid out in randomized complete block design with five replications. Fertilizer was 80-26-33 kg NPK/ha, 23 kg Zn/ha, and 100 kg gypsum/ha.

Filled spikelets (specific gravity = 1.10) of each harvest were separated with salt solution and dried at 80 °C for 5 d.

Husk and kernel weights were determined for 100 g seed/season per

Table 1. Varietal difference in HKR in 3 seasons. BRRI, Gazipur, 1985-86.

Variety	HKR		
	Transplanted aus	Transplanted aman	Boro
BR1	0.256 ± 0.002	0.232 ± 0.004	0.229 ± 0.004
BR3	0.269 ± 0.003	0.261 ± 0.001	0.263 ± 0.004
BR9	0.290 ± 0.002	0.261 ± 0.003	0.260 ± 0.001
BR12	0.267 ± 0.003	0.253 ± 0.002	0.250 ± 0.003
BR16	0.267 ± 0.002	0.259 ± 0.002	0.258 ± 0.001
Av	0.270	0.253	0.252

Table 2. Genetic parameters for HKR in 3 seasons.^a BRRI, Gazipur, 1985–86.

Season	Range	Mean	Variance ratio ^b	PCV	GCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Mean genetic advance (%)
Transplanted aus	0.250–0.298	0.270	36.53**	5.377	5.035	1.888	87.66	9.71
Transplanted aman	0.227–0.273	0.253	24.96**	5.280	4.803	2.194	82.74	9.00
Boro	0.222–0.276	0.252	31.21**	5.937	5.500	2.237	85.79	10.49

^aPCV = phenotypic coefficient of variability, GCV = genotypic coefficient of variability, ECV = environmental coefficient of variability. ^b** = significant at 1% level.

replication. A rubber dehusker was used to dehull the grain.

The HKRs (husk weight divided by kernel weight) of a variety in transplanted aman and boro seasons were similar but numerically higher than those in

transplanted aus, which had comparatively lower spikelet fills.

Clear HKR differences occurred in the five varieties. HKR variation was wide and environmental coefficient of variability was low in all seasons, indicating that HKR

is less responsive to environmental factors. Heritability for HKR was high; genetic advance was more or less similar in the three seasons. HKR may be a nearly stable indicator in screening for cultivars with lower husk content. □

Lectins in living organisms interact with silicon

N. E. Alyoshin, E. R. Avakyan, E. M. Sorochinskaya, N. G. Turnanyan, and E. P. Alyoshin, Krasnodar Agricultural Biotechnological Centre, P.O. Belozernoe, Krasnodar 353204, USSR

An unspecified interaction of lectins with silicon compounds exists in the tissues of silicophiles, both in living organisms and in histological preparations. Scientists need to consider this phenomenon when they use lectins, immunochemicals, and their dyes in silicophile studies.

Lectin preparations (including stains) were previously considered to interact specifically with sugars or their residues.

Silica structures of the rice husk of Krasnodarsky 424. Microspodography × 20

We have shown that during rice husk microspodography the lectins interact actively with silicon compounds that are present in large amounts in silicophile tissues (see figure). Silica can comprise up to 20% of some rice tissue dry matter.

Attention to this may prevent erroneous conclusions that interactions were with sugars rather than with silicon compounds. □

Grain quality

Grain quality of F₁ rice hybrids

Y. P. Khanna, J. S. Bijral, T. R. Sharma, B. B. Gupta, C. L. Raina, and K. S. Kanwal, SKUAST, Regional Agriculture Research Station (RARS), R. S. Pura (Jammu) 181102, India

Nine rice hybrids developed at RARS and check cultivar Jaya were evaluated for physicochemical and cooked rice characteristics. Standard methods were used to analyze dried grain with about 12% moisture content. Recovery varied from 78 to 80% for hulling and from 72.5 to 75.5% for milling. Five of the hybrids

showed significantly higher head rice recovery than Jaya (RHR1, RHR4, RHR6, RHR7, and RHR9). The rest (except RHR5) were statistically at par with Jaya (see table). Head rice recovery was very high, which suggests undermilling of rice by a Kett Polisher (model TP 20).

Physicochemical characters of F₁ rice hybrids^a at RARS, R. S. Pura, India.

Hybrid or variety	Cross combination	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)	Head rice (%)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	L/W ratio	Abdominal white ^b	Alkali spreading value	Water uptake (%)	Volume expansion ratio	Elongation ratio	Amylose (%)
RHR1	Zhen Shan 97 A/IR3 1868	80.0	75.0	73.5	5.60	2.27	2.47	OP	2.0	165	3.7	1.7	19.2
RHR2	V20 A/IR31802	78.0	73.0	68.5	6.65	2.26	2.94	Present	2.0	160	4.0	1.5	17.0
RHR3	Zhen Shan 97 A/IR8585	78.0	72.5	70.0	5.84	2.41	2.42	Present	4.0	170	3.7	1.6	17.0
RHR4	Zhen Shan 97 A/IR31802	78.5	75.5	72.0	5.67	2.36	2.40	Absent	2.0	150	3.7	1.7	17.0
RHR5	Zhen Shan 97 A/IET1410	78.0	73.5	68.0	6.98	1.99	3.51	Absent	6.0	350	3.7	1.5	20.3
RHR6	Zhen Shan 97 A/VL 15	79.5	74.5	70.5	5.66	2.71	2.09	Present	3.0	200	3.7	1.4	20.9
RHR7	VA20 A/IR3 1851	79.5	74.0	71.0	6.59	2.34	2.82	Present	3.0	140	3.7	1.5	17.5
RHR8	IR48483 A/IR83619	78.0	73.0	69.5	6.14	2.39	2.57	OP	3.0	150	3.7	1.6	16.0
RHR9	IR46830 A/IR36	79.0	74.0	71.0	6.62	2.09	3.17	Absent	2.0	140	3.7	1.5	19.2
Jaya	Check	79.0	74.5	69.0	6.37	2.57	2.48	Present	7.0	350	4.0	1.7	29.6
	LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.7	1.2	0.36	0.14	—	—	1.3	59	0.7	0.1	2.70

^aAv of 2 replications. ^bOP = occasionally present.